

The Hijra Body as Performance in Select Autobiographical Writing

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Abstract: *This paper examines the construction of gender identity through gender performance in Me Hijra, Me Laxmi by Laxmi and The Truth About Me: A Hijra Life Story by A. Revathi. Through a critical analysis of the selected autobiographies, this paper explores the constant regulation of hijra bodies in mainstream society and within their community. To achieve the objective of this study, Judith Butler's theory of performativity, as developed in her texts Gender Trouble (1990) and Bodies That Matter (1993), has been applied to explore the hijra body as a site of gender performance. The narratives of Laxmi and Revathi reveal how they performed as cisgender children to meet the demands of a heteronormative society and later as hijras to feel a sense of belongingness among the hijras. These acts illustrate how they negotiated their gender identity to fit both dominant social expectations and the normative frameworks of the hijra community.*

Keywords: *hijra body, gender performativity, gender identity, transgender narratives, gender binary.*

1. Introduction

The hijra body, in the South Asian context, has become a cultural space where gender identity and experiences have been expressed through repeated performances. It is through acts such as their distinct fashion of begging, or performing *badhai* at weddings and childbirth, that the hijra body gains visibility and offers an understanding of their gender identity. The hijra body as performance thus situates them as a living enactment of identity.

A hijra is “an individual born biologically male but exhibiting feminine gender traits that situate them in a liminal space, termed as the ‘third gender’ in society” (Hazarika 2). The Hijra community is an established group in Indian society with their own distinct history, tradition and rules that are unique to its culture. They generally comprise individuals who were born as a biological male and later transitioned to a female, thus falling under the third gender category.

The existence of such a culture to call their own provides meaning to the lives of hijras, who have to go through unpleasant experiences to achieve their desire to transition to a woman. According to Serena Nanda, the idea of hijra may refer to “not only divesting oneself of one’s masculine identity, but also taking on a feminine one” (Nanda 2). Therefore, the Hijras who are originally born as biological males first have to shed their gender identity associated with biological sex and embrace femininity in fulfilment of their desires. In this regard, the culture of the Hijra community performs the role of the mother who welcomes this beautiful change and provides them with a home where they find a family to call their own. The hijras fall under the broader category of “transgender” and belong to a distinct cultural group of transgender women who take on feminine roles within familial structures and follow a unique set of gender norms (Kalra 123). These performances by hijra individuals are continuously reproduced as the enforcement of such gender norms is expected of them, and are passed down from one generation to the next, as each hijra is taught how to behave like one by their elders when they join the community.

This paper examines the construction of gender identity through gender performance in hijra autobiographical writing. The study offers a critical analysis of

three hijra autobiographies which includes Laxmi's *Me Hijra, Me Laxmi* and A. Revathi *The Truth About Me: A Hijra Life Story*. To achieve the objective of this study, Judith Butler's theory of performativity has been applied to explore the hijra body as a site for gender performance, based on her texts *Gender Trouble* (1990) and *Bodies That Matter* (1993). In doing so, the paper positions hijra life writing as a critical intervention that challenges binary constructions of gender and re-claims agency over marginalised bodies.

2. Review of Literature

A transgender person is someone "whose gender identity or expression does not align with culturally held expectations for people who share their assigned sex at birth" (King et al 1). While a person's gender identity is determined by their psychological idea of gender which they perceive internally, such a concept is often overlooked when it comes to understanding the gender identity of transgender individuals (Buck 465).

Transgender narratives in India, especially autobiographies, are "a call for reformation in the diseased gender norms of our society" (Nair 15). The first transgender narrative published by A. Revathi, which is titled *Unarvum Uruvum (Our Lives, Our Words)* in 2004, has contributed significantly to the writing of transgender narratives and their publication in India in the twenty-first century (Preeti & Kaur 170).

Transgender autobiographies reflect the dual consciousness of the self that negotiates between cultural definitions and is also seen as different from such definitions among transgender individuals (Baruah 47). Baruah also highlights how transgender individuals fail "to recognise themselves in the reflections of cultural representations" (Baruah 47).

In "Power Trouble: Performativity as Critical Theory", Allen draws on Butler's theory of performativity, especially in understanding how power works and offers insights on how power can be resisted. Yet, she points out, some critical feminist theorists have failed to acknowledge the significance of Butler's theory (Allen 456). While most feminist theorists focus only on either how power is established and maintained or explore the possibilities of resisting and subverting power, Butler's theory attempts to address both of these issues (Allen 457).

Allen breaks down the progression of Butler's theory of performativity from its initial formulation in *Gender Trouble* (1990) to its subsequent reworking in *Bodies That Matter* (1993). She emphasises that while Butler, in *Gender Trouble*, incorporates Foucault's idea of power and navigates how it operates through and, at the same time, shapes subjects, social norms and discourse, she struggles to account for agency and resistance (Allen 459-461). This theory is revised in *Bodies That Matter* (1993), in which she borrows Derrida's idea of citationality. Butler revisits the concept of repetition in gender performance, but notes that each repetition introduces a change, and each change in repetition creates space for resistance and agency (Allen 462-463).

Julie Wight sheds light on the hostility, social exclusion and discrimination subjected to by transgender individuals due to their non-normative behaviour, which treats gender as binary, closely linked to biological sex and heterosexuality (Wight 73). She pointed out how Butler's theory of performativity has been instrumental in understanding gender as a social construct produced through repetition, shaped by culture, history, language and power (Wight 73-74). Wight argued that while such concepts question gender binaries at a theoretical level, gender norms

are still actively practised in reality.

Building on Butler's arguments, Wight states that a person is gendered before they are assigned any other identity. As a matter of fact, a person is assigned a gender as a baby before they develop the tools to resist such identities by adults based on their biological sex (Wight 75). Wight points out that such practices complicate the position of transgender individuals whose identities lie beyond the gender binaries of biology, culture and linguistics (Wight 76). She argues that though Butler's theory suggests how the repetition of acts contributes to the construction of gender, it fails to control how these acts are perceived or interpreted by the observer (Wight 77).

3.Theoretical Framework:

This study incorporates Judith Butler's theory of performativity as its central theoretical lens to explore the hijra body as a site for gender performance. While Butler's theory heavily draws on feminist criticism, this paper applies the same to examine the formulation of gender identities among hijra individuals through a textual analysis of selected autobiographies titled *Me Hijra*, *Me Laxmi* by Laxmi and *The Truth About Me: A Hijra Life Story* by A. Revathi.

Judith Butler, in her phenomenal book titled *Gender Trouble: Feminism and the Subversion of Identity* (1990), states that sex and gender are not co-related and are distinct categories of identity, where sex is a biological category, and gender is the product of social and cultural norms. She challenges the idea that gender is stable and occurs naturally. She argues that the illusion of gender as a fixed category is constructed through the repetition of acts such as behaviour, posture, gestures, clothing, etc., regulated by strict social norms, where those who deviate from such gender norms are marginalised.

In *Bodies That Matter* (1993), Butler asserts that the power in the construction of the identity of queer people lies in repetition. She adds that performativity does not come into force just because someone intends it or holds power as an individual. Performativity only works when certain norms are repeated continuously. She points out that while it is important to label identity categories such as "women", "queer", "lesbian", etc., from a political standpoint, such labels are theoretically unstable and inaccurate as they fail to fully capture the complexity of a person's gender identity. However, she suggests that the strength of queer politics lies in keeping the term open and unstable.

The hijra body, due to their cultural practices, becomes a site for the performance of practising their set of norms, such as the way they speak, dress, behave, perform rituals, etc. Through the repetition of such acts over time, they have constructed a distinct identity, which is both gendered and cultural. While Butler's arguments on gender performativity mainly deal with the gender binary of male and female, her discussion on queer performativity creates space for understanding gendered bodies that deviate from established gender norms, such as the hijras.

The selected hijra autobiographies serve as a rich textual site for this study to explore and examine the construction of their gender identity through performativity. Through the narratives of Laxmi, Vidya and Revathi, the autobiographies also demonstrate how repeating acts differently over time enables the expression of resistance and agency.

4.Methodology:

This study incorporates qualitative research methodology with descriptive and narrative approaches as its research methods. The study draws three autobiograph-

ical texts, titled *Me Hijra, Me Laxmi* by Laxmi and *The Truth About Me: A Hijra Life Story* by A. Revathi as its primary sources. The selected texts give us a first-hand insight into the lived experiences and gender negotiations of hijra individuals. While each autobiography has independently contributed to this study, a single narrative has been framed by coalescing data from all three texts.

Academic articles and theoretical works on gender, performance and hijras, including Butler's *Gender Trouble: Feminism and the Subversion of Identity* (1990) and *Bodies That Matter* (1993), have been used as secondary sources to contextualise and support the interpretations of the primary texts.

The study aims to examine the hijra body as a site for gender performativity. Thus, the scope of the study is limited to analysing the gender and cultural norms practised by the hijra community, and does not extend to the study of the broader umbrella of the term 'transgender'. The pronouns 'she' and 'her' have been used to address each hijra individual, as mentioned in the selected autobiographies. Judith Butler's theory of performativity, which has been applied as the principal theoretical framework, has been primarily borrowed from her book titled *Gender Trouble: Feminism and the Subversion of Identity* (1990) for this study, while only the final chapter of *Bodies That Matter* (1993) titled "Critically Queer" has been referred to, to explore gender performativity among queer people.

To describe the events and situations from the autobiography that support the study, a descriptive research method has been employed. The narrative research method has also been used in the study to analyse the personal narratives of Laxmi, Vidya and Revathi.

The findings of this study are limited to personal narratives and must not be treated as ethnographic data, as autobiographical writing often risks being a one-sided representation and may not account for the entire community.

5. Findings:

In the autobiographies of Laxmi and Revathi, performativity begins long before they come to identify as hijras. From an early age, they begin to realise that their gender identity does not correspond with their biological sex. However, due to a lack of awareness, they internalise the belief that something is wrong with them and, fearing punishment for deviation from gender norms, they begin to perform cisgender role regulated by dominant socio-cultural norms.

In *Me Hijra, Me Laxmi*, Laxmi revealed being self-conscious because she was an expert dancer, but it feminised her body (Laxmi 27). From a very young age, we can see the instability in her gender expression, which later culminated in her joining the hijra community and strictly following their established gender and cultural norms. In her autobiography, she described how she juggled between two roles, i.e., of a dutiful son in front of her parents and dressing up in female attire when she could be herself with prying eyes. She sometimes "picked up courage and landed on campus in female attire" (Laxmi 30). Although she did not fully understand herself yet, she revealed her wish to express her gender through clothing. She wrote, "I liked being a drag queen. But then drag queens cross-dressed only sporadically, for shows, whereas I wanted to drape myself in a sari and wear skirts every single day" (Laxmi 33). However, she also added, "My family didn't have an inkling of any of this. To them, I was Laxminarayan, the eldest son of the family who went to college and had a job" (Laxmi 33).

A turning point in Laxmi's life arrived when she had the chance to meet a hijra named Shabina. For a long time, until this moment, Laxmi was made to be-

lieve that she was gay since she was attracted to men. To Laxmi, being gay did not make complete sense because she knew that she identified as a woman and wanted to become one. All her doubts were answered when she met Shabina:

“Shabina was a hijra. She was dressed in a sari. She looked every bit a woman from head to toe. Everything about her – her speech, her gait, her mannerisms, and her voice – was so feminine. I knew at that very moment that I yearned to be like Shabina.” (Laxmi 38)

This shows that it was femininity that Laxmi had sought to embrace. Laxmi’s desire to wear feminine clothing every day came face-to-face with its human form as Shabina, whose gender identity gave meaning to everything that Laxmi had felt about herself but could not understand. Soon after, with the crowning of a dupatta over her head and a gift of two green sarees, Laxmi’s *reet* or christening ceremony was complete, and she had officially become a hijra.

This event holds great significance to a Hijra who had spent all her life as a misfit in society. She did not feel like a male, the body she was born with. Nor was she accepted as a woman. In fact, she was ridiculed and faced harassment and abuse on multiple occasions for behaving outside the gender norms assigned to their biological sex. As a member of the hijra community, she now has a family of her own, and she now has an identity outside the socially constructed binary of male and female. She now has an identity as a third gender and a hijra. Laxmi expresses the same in her autobiography and writes, “I was a hijra. I had my own identity. No longer did I feel like an alien” (Laxmi 43).

The significance of such rituals that declare the gender identity of an individual can only be sustained through repeated performance over time. Each time a new hijra is introduced to the community, the *reet* is performed, establishing this act as a norm among hijra individuals. However, Laxmi’s dual performance of gender, one as a cisgender son and the other as a hijra, had continued even after he became a hijra. This was evident when Laxmi had disclosed to Lataguru, soon after her *reet* ceremony, that she performed the role of a son at her biological parents’ house, where he wore male clothing and could not afford to wear a saree (Laxmi 44). Laxmi had to negotiate between her performance of two kinds of gender identity: one that was expected of her, and the other, which she identified with and had chosen out of her free will. She wrote:

“Gradually, I restricted my use of male clothing to the house and started to wear saris whenever I went out. People knew I wore saris when there was a performance and, in the beginning, I used that as an excuse, telling them I was headed for this and that show, or this or that rehearsal. But when they saw me in a saree all the time, they smelled a rat.” (Laxmi 46)

Laxmi soon lost her autonomy to perform as a male for her parents, which she described as “bone of contention” between her biological family and her, after Lataguru moved to the apartment above her biological parents’ and urged Laxmi to live with her and wear a saree at all times (Laxmi 73 -74). This reflects how gender has been regulated even within the hijra socio-cultural norms.

Laxmi also outlined a distinct set of norms that she encountered within hijra cultural practices:

“These concerns everyday things like how a hijra must walk, how she must serve water to a visitor. While serving water, the glass must not be held at the top or middle. Instead, the glass must be balanced on palms joined together. The pallu of the hijra’s mustn’t touch anyone as she moves around. One should not lie with

one's feet facing the guru. The guru's clothes must not be worn by the chela, nor should she utter her guru's or gharana's name. The hijra should not talk back to her guru. And so on." (Laxmi 159)

This reveals how, for a hijra individual, basic everyday acts such as the way they walk, speak, dress, and move, etc., become a performance. They always remain under the watchful eyes of their elders and other members of the community who make sure their performances are regulated within the hijra socio-cultural framework.

The hijra performance is also extended to their training for survival against the mainstream heteronormative society. The hijras, due to their gender nonconformity, often face harassment and gender-based discrimination. Due to limited employment opportunities, they resort to begging or sex work for survival. As a measure of self-defence, they adapt certain tactics and perform them in their everyday lives during their interaction with the mainstream population.

In her autobiography, Laxmi has given explicit details on such performances as tactics for survival:

"The hijra is told to isolate herself from mainstream society. She is taught to clap with her palms pressed together to create a firecracker-like sound, how to beg, and how to flatter. She is also taught how to harass in order to extract money. This is the hijra's revenge on society for ostracizing her...The aggressive body language of hijras scares people off, but it is something we have cultivated as a survival tactic." (Laxmi 175-178).

These excerpts from Laxmi's autobiography underscore the performative character of hijra socio-cultural norms. Revathi's autobiography, titled *The Truth About Me: A Hijra Life Story* (2010), engages with similar themes of dual gender performances. Like Laxmi, Revathi also enjoyed dancing and wearing female attire. Her family, especially her brothers, were strictly against such acts, and this would often result in Revathi being thrashed by her brothers.

Laxmi and Revathi have had different experiences of acceptance from their biological families. Laxmi's parents had accepted her identity as a hijra and her role towards her second family of hijras. Revathi's biological family, however, responded with hostility and subjected her to considerable hardship. As a child, Revathi had run away from her home to be with her guru at just ten years old. She was often assaulted by her biological family for exhibiting feminine traits, and her home had become a space of gender regulation within strict gender norms. In both cases, there is a transition from normative kinship to performative kinship, where they move from blood ties to their chosen families.

Revathi's first meeting with the hijras, followed by her *reet* ceremony, had resulted in her being away from home for over a month. When she had returned, her hair had grown longer than social standards for males. She told her family that she had gone to see a temple festival and that she had grown her hair as an offering to Tirupati (Laxmi 30-31). Revathi then continued to perform the role of a male even though she had now become a hijra.

The hijra community live within familial structures (*parivar*), and each hijra individual performs a feminine role. Revathi described the typical structure of the *parivar* (family) of the *naik* or the head of a *gharana*, which includes the *guru* (mother), the *gurubai* (sister), the *chela* (daughter) and so on. Revathi also listed out the terms as explained to her by her *guru*:

"*Badudaadi* – great-grandmother's *guru*

Daadaguru – grandmother's *guru* (great-grandmother)

Nanaguru – *guru's guru* (grandmother)

Guru – mother

Kaalaguru – *guru's sister*

Gurubai – sister, *Badagurubau* – elder sister

Chotagurubai – younger sister

Chela – daughter, *Naathi-chela* – granddaughter

Chandichela – great-granddaughter

Sadak-naathi – great granddaughter's daughter" (2010, p. 64)

It is also customary for a Hijra to perform the *chatai* ceremony on the Tija of Muharram, during which they choose ten Hijras as their *chelas*. This ceremony is considered to be of great importance to the Hijra community (Laxmi 51). In this manner, a Hijra builds her family. The idea of being a *guru* is associated with wisdom rather than with age in the Hijra community (Laxmi 53). Thus, the hijras perform both maternal and filial roles as the *guru* and the *chela*.

A large number of hijras undergo castration to feel complete as a symbol of shedding away the maleness from their bodies. This may be interpreted as an act of submission to the hijra gender norm, while at the same time, this may be seen as an act of subversion against the normative social norms. In the hijra community, this process is called '*nirvana*'. Though it is a common belief that all hijras are castrated, it is, in fact, not mandatory for a Hijra to do so and depends completely on her will. Hijras do not encourage forceful castration or associate it with the notion of being a 'real' Hijra. Laxmi is one such example (Laxmi 156).

On the other hand, those hijras such as Revathi, who chose to have '*nirvana*' done, do not simply undergo castration but go through a set of rituals before they consider the whole process complete. Before anything, they are given a choice to pick if they want to get their '*nirvana*' done by a *thayamma* (by a hijra without the use of anaesthesia) or by a doctor in a hospital (Revathi 66). This reflects how the gender performance of hijras is not restricted to body language but also through embodied practices that involve the transformation of the body.

Like Laxmi, Revathi was also introduced to a set of norms and restrictions governing conduct within her hijra family. After Revathi had her *nirvana* done, she was advised to behave like a woman, for now she had become one, within the code of conduct of the hijras. She was not allowed to cut her hair or go back to her biological family (Revathi 89). Revathi observed:

"A hijra can become chela to anyone, but must ultimately live only with her nani or guru and abide by what they say. A hijra must necessarily follow the rules of the community: if she fails, she is bound to suffer...If I listened to my guru and nani, I too would attain their status and achieve the freedom they possessed, when I was their age." (Revathi 99)

This reflects how the hijra socio-cultural norms were regulated through power, where one must perform to maintain their gender identity, and any deviation from the norm was met with punishment or suffering. Additionally, they were conditioned to believe that consistently performing as per the gender norms of the hijras would reward them with the same freedom and power that their elders possessed.

6. Conclusion:

This study has explored and examined the narratives of Laxmi and Revathi to understand how the hijra body serves as a performative site for the construction and maintenance of their gender identity. Drawing on Judith Butler's theory of performativity, the study demonstrates how gender is unstable and requires repeated performances over time to both constitute and contest identity.

The hijra body becomes a medium of gender expression and survival. In the case of Laxmi and Revathi, we observe how their bodies had become sites for dual performances of gender: the performance of a cisgender person in spaces where freely expressing their gender identity could bring them danger and the performance that they had to put up to become the gender that they had chosen. However, both these performances were regulated by two opposing sets of socio-cultural norms. In spaces where they performed the role of a cisgender person, their act was regulated by the dominant social norms. And in spaces where they performed the role of a hijra, their performances were regulated by strict hijra socio-cultural norms.

While Butler's theory of performativity is Western in thought, this study has moved beyond just challenging the gender binary of male/female articulated within this framework. The study of hijra narratives recontextualises Butler's theory of performativity within a South Asian epistemic framework, which encompasses not only gender identity, but also culture, spirituality, kinship and collective belonging. This expands Butler's theory and situates performativity as the politics of the body and a medium for survival.

The repetition of the gender performance of hijras has transformed something that was previously considered a stigma into a tool for visibility. The very act that previously marginalised them subsequently became a source of agency. Performativity, thus, had emerged as an act of self-expression, and the performative body came to be constituted as an instrument of transformation.

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